

Beta-Ketoanilides as Reagents in Inorganic Analysis

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β -Ketoanilides may be considered as substituted β -diketones as the same group is involved in the chelation. Four such reagents, acetoacetanilide, benzoylacetanilide, benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide and cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide have been used in the gravimetric and extraction-spectrophotometric determination of various metal ions and their separation from foreign ions. The relative merit as a gravimetric and as a spectrophotometric reagent depends on the nature of substitution. The effect of substitution on the nature of chelates of several derivatives of acetoacetanilide have been studied. Indirect titrimetric methods for beryllium involving the bromination of the anilide group have also been developed. The use of a thio-derivative, acetothioacetanilide has been reported.

ORGANIC ligands with two carbonyl groups separated from each other by a methylene group of general formula $R_1 \cdot CO \cdot CH_2 \cdot CO \cdot R_2$, constitute an important class of reagents used in the analysis of various metal ions. The enol-forms are mainly responsible for the activity of these ligands. The β -diketones ($R_1, R_2 = \text{alkyl or aryl group}$) constitute the simplest family of this class of compounds and have been extensively used in the extraction and photometric determination of various metal ions as well as their separation by fractional volatilisation of the chelates. The chelates of several β -ketoesters obtained by the substitution of one alkoxy group for R_1 or R_2 , have also been studied well. The next step is the substitution of one '-NH.C₆H₅' group in one of the terminal 'R's of the β -diketone. The resulting reagents are solid compounds. The first reagent, acetoacetanilide¹ has been introduced by the author through the gravimetric determination of beryllium.

Considerable progress has been made in the preparation of chelate compounds and upon their structures related to the simple geometry of ring formation. But understanding the nature of the complexes on the basis of (i) electron density of the donor, (ii) resonance interaction between the chelate ring and its aromatic substituents, (iii) steric effects of the substituents as well as the acid dissociation constant of the ligand is necessary for the development of analytical reagents. Extensive studies on the complexes are now being carried out with various β -ketoanilides. Such compounds with desired substituents in the benzene ring of the anilide group are easy to prepare.

Acetoacetanilide (HAA): A derivative of acetylacetone.

Numerous derivatives of acetylacetone, the simplest β -diketone, have been prepared and the nature of their chelates have been studied. The important derivatives are obtained by the substitution of suitable groups in the terminal positions (R_1, R_2) of acetylacetone, because substitution in the active methylene group often causes steric hindrance which reduces the stability

of the chelates due to prevention of the planar configuration of the chelate ring. The substitution in terminal position, on the other hand, affects the ratio of the keto-enol tautomerism as well as the resonance between the two carbonyl groups both of which in turn determine the stability of the metal chelates. The nature of the substituent (hydrophobic, chromophoric etc.) also influence the applicability of the ligand as an analytical reagent.

The introduction of an ethoxy group in one of the terminal positions of acetylacetone will result in ethylacetoacetate. The strong ester resonance would normally strengthen the 'O-metal' bond in its chelates by increasing the negative charge on the oxygen. In fact the beryllium-ethylacetoacetate complex in 50% dioxan medium is more stable than the corresponding acetylacetone chelate². However, in these β -ketoesters the participation by the carbonyl groups in the ester resonance may greatly interfere with the chelate resonance. As a result the tendency of the increment in the oxygen-metal bond strength by the ester resonance may be out-weighed by the effect of the weakening of the bond due to participation of carbonyl resonance with ester resonance. Thus, the acetylacetone complex of copper(II) is more stable than the corresponding ethylacetoacetate chelate³.

The adverse effect on chelation due to the ester resonance may be overcome by the substitution of an anilide group in place of the ethoxy group. The introduction of this hydrophobic group as well as the increase in molecular weight in acetoacetanilide will result in the decreased solubility in water and enhanced extractibility of the chelates. The possibility of bromination of the anilide group of the chelates of these β -ketoanilides will also provide a titrimetric method for the determination of metals.

Acetoacetanilide has the possibility of acting as an ambidentate ligand as co-ordination through nitrogen (1):

is possible in addition to the expected linkages through oxygen atoms (II, III). However, the resonating

Structures I, II, III

structures of amide group (IV), suggest the donation through oxygen because of its higher electronegativity⁴.

Structure IV

By studying the effects of substitution in the benzene ring Harries² concluded that in the beryllium-acetoacetanilide chelate the bonding takes place through two oxygen atoms. Similar observations were reported for copper(II) chelates using mass and i.r. spectroscopy⁵.

Benzoylacetanilide (HBA)

Uitert⁶ *et al* observed that β -diketones having two aromatic rings as end groups form more stable chelate compounds than those with an aliphatic end group for comparable pK_a values. The author recommended the use of benzoylacetanilide as an analytical reagent in which the terminal methyl group of HAA is replaced by a benzene ring which affect the enolate resonance

Structure V

resulting in a higher degree of dissociation of the proton. The resulting complexes are more stable and more insoluble in water than the corresponding HAA chelates. The increased conjugation in these chelates (V) renders HBA more promising for use in spectrophotometry.

Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide (HBNA)

The introduction of a nitro group in the benzene ring of the anilide group is expected to increase the enolisation of the reagent. The presence of the chromophoric nitro group has also made the spectrophotometric determination of beryllium in the visible range feasible. The λ_{max} for the UO_2 -complex of HBNA exhibit a shift to higher wave length than the corresponding chelate with HBA though the molar absorptivity and sensitivity remains practically unaltered. The substitution of the nitro group in the meta-

position causes no steric hindrance in the chelates (VI). Ketterup *et al*^{7,8} have studied the stabilities of UO_2^{2+} and Be^{2+} -complexes of aceto-*m*-nitroacetanilide along with other derivatives of HAA and related them to the mesomeric and electromeric effects due to substitution.

Structure VI

Cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide (HCPCA)

The fusion of an alicyclic ring with the chelate ring has shown interesting effects in many instances. Thus, 1-2-cyclohexanedione dixime⁹ is a more sensitive reagent for nickel than dimethylglyoxime and 1-2-diaminocyclohexane tetraacetate¹⁰ forms a stronger chelate than ethylenediamine tetraacetate does. The pK_a value of HCPCA is comparable to that of HBA, but due to the presence of alicyclic ring the reagents

Structure VII

absorb at lower wave length permitting the spectrophotometric determination of colourless metal ions feasible in the U.V.-region. The chelates (VII) are quite stable as the chelate ring is fused with the alicyclic ring.

Properties of the β -ketoanilides used as Analytical Reagents

All the reagents are stable and no special precautions are required for preserving them. The reagents are generally prepared by the condensation of aniline or its suitable derivative with the appropriate β -ketoester. This is a simple process except in the case of HCPCA, where a separation of the β -ketoanilide from anililide is necessary. Two of the reagents, HAA and HBNA are available commercially. All of these compounds are appreciably soluble in aqueous ethanol. HCPCA can also be used as the sodium salt prepared by dissolving it in 1% sodium hydroxide solution and neutralising the excess alkali with dilute acid. All of them except HBNA give colourless solutions in isobutylmethyl ketone (hexone). The properties of the reagents are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROPERTIES OF β -KETOANILIDES USED AS ANALYTICAL REAGENT

Reagent	m. p. °C	Colour	λ_{max} (nm) (a)	pK (75%acetone)	Reference for preparation.
Acetoacetanilide HAA	85	White	<320	11.6(b)	11,12
Benzoylacetanilide HBAA	106-106.5	White	340	10.0	13-15
Benzoyl <i>m</i> -nitroacetanilide HBNA	136-137	Yellow	375	9.4	16
Cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide HCPCA	103-104	White	<300	10.1	17

(a) in hexone ; (b) in 50% water-dioxan.

Applications in Gravimetric Analysis

All the four reagents have been used in the gravimetric determination of metal ions, particularly the hard-acid¹⁸ (class a)¹⁹ type ions like Be(II), Al(III), Ti(IV), U(VI) etc. HBNA has been found to be the best of the four for gravimetric analysis. This reagent has also been used as a precipitant for metal ions like Co(II), Ni(II), Mn(II), and Cd(II). The experimental conditions for the precipitation and determination of various metals are listed in Table 2. All the complexes were weighed directly after drying.

first organic reagent for beryllium giving weighable chelate. The lowest pH for quantitative precipitation of beryllium has been related to the pK_a of the β -ketoanilide. HBNA is the best precipitant for beryllium while HCPCA is equally good for gravimetric, spectrophotometric and titrimetric determination. The uranium complexes are very much pH sensitive and generally contain two molecules of water. The use of pyridine to control the pH of precipitation improved the nature of the complex. Several soft-acid type metal ions have

TABLE 2—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATIONS

Reagent	Metal ion	Composition	Colour	Drying Temp. (°C)	pH	Ref.
HAA	Be(II)	Be(AA) ₂	White	110	5.5-8.2	1
	Cu(II)	Cu(AA) ₂	Green	110	5.5-6.8 5.9-7.9	20
HBA	Be(III)	Be(BA) ₂	White	105	6.4-7.9	15
	Hg(II)	Hg(BA) ₂	White	120	3.1-7.0	21
	Al(III)	Al(BA) ₃	White	95	6.5-8.0	22
	Ti(IV)	TiO(BA) ₂	Orange yellow	110	0.9-2.0	15
	V(IV)	VO(BA) ₂	Green	110	3.0-7.1	21
	U(VI)	UO ₂ (BA) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Orange red	120	6.0-6.6	23
	Be(II)	Be(BNA) ₂	Yellow	120	6.5-9.0	24
U(VI)	(a) UO ₂ (BNA) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Vermillion red	120	(a) 5.8	25	
	(b) UO ₂ (BNA) ₂ .NH ₃ .H ₂ O			(b) 6.7-7.8		
HBNA	Hg(II)	Hg(BNA) ₂	Light yellow	120	2.5-9.0	26
	V(IV)	VO(BNA) ₂	Light blue	110	4.0-5.5	27
HBNA	Mn(II)	Mn(BNA) ₂	Yellow	120	6.4-7.5	28
	Co(II)	Co(BNA) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Yellow	120	5.4-7.0	29
	Ni(II)	Ni(BNA) ₂	Yellow	120	6.5-7.5	29
	Cd(II)	Cd(BNA) ₂	Yellow	110	6.8-8.5	30
	Be(II)	Be(CPCA) ₂	White	120	5.9-8.1	31
HCPCA	U(VI)	UO ₂ (CPCA) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Orange yellow	120	6.8-8.0	32
	Hg(II)	Hg(CPCA) ₂	White	105	5.5-8.6	33
	V(IV)	VO(CPCA) ₂	Light blue	110	5.0-6.0	34
	Mo(VI)	MoO ₂ (CPCA) ₂	Yellow	120	0.5-2.5	28

(a) in the presence of pyridine ; (b) in the presence of ammonia

Beryllium, in quantities as low as 0.6 to 4.0 mg has been determined with these reagents with relative standard deviation of 0.26% in case of HBNA and HCPCA. The precipitation becomes specific in the presence of Na₂-EDTA or Mg-EDTA. HAA is the

also been determined. Thus HBA, HBNA and HCPCA have been used in the gravimetric determination of mercury(II) and its separation from other metal ions including Ag(I), Th(I), Cu(II), Cd(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) etc.

The separation of metal ions is possible by pH-controlled precipitation with the β -ketoanilides. However, the use of suitable masking agents for the foreign ions during the precipitation of a particular metal ion has been preferred in order to develop simple procedures for the estimation of the desired metal in its important ores and alloys. Examples of such separations are listed in Table 3, in which the oxidation numbers of the foreign metal ions have been omitted unless they are uncommon states. The masking agent, if necessary for any of the foreign ions is chosen from the list given in the second column.

Some interesting separations have also been effected by the combination of masking agent and control of pH. For example, a mixture containing nickel and

cobalt is adjusted to pH 3.5-4.0, ammonium thiocyanate is added and cobalt is precipitated quantitatively with HBNA at pH 8.5. The filtrate is boiled with hydrochloric acid and nickel is determined gravimetrically with the same reagent at pH 7.0.

Applications in Spectrophotometric Analysis

Uranium(VI) has been determined spectrophotometrically with all of these reagents while beryllium has been determined with HBNA and HCPCA. The reactions with HCPCA were very sensitive with both these metal ions. Table 4 shows that other metal ions, e. g. Cu(II), Hg(II), Fe(III), Ti(IV), V(IV) and Mo(VI) have also been determined spectrophotometrically with these reagents.

TABLE 3—SEPARATION FROM DIVERSE IONS BY PREPARATION

Complex precipitated	Masking agents	Foreign metals*	Applications
Be(AA) ₂	a,c	Ca, Mg, Zn, Cu, Co, Ni, Al, Fe, U, Ti	Beryl
Be(BA) ₂	b,c,d	Cu, Zn, Ni, Co, Al, Fe, Cr, Ce(III), Ti, V(IV), U, Mo, W.	Beryl
Be(BNA) ₂	b,c,m	Pb, Cu, Co, Ni, Zn, Mn, Al, Fe, Cr, Ce(IV), Th, Ti, V(IV), U.	Beryl
Be(CPCA) ₂	a	Pb, Cu, Co, Ni, Al, Fe, Ce(III), Th, Ti, V(IV), U.	Beryl
UO ₂ (BA) ₂ .2H ₂ O	b,g,h	Be, Pb, Co, Ni, Bi, Fe, Al, Cr, Ce(III), V(IV), Th, Zr, Mo.	Uraninite
UO ₂ (BNA) ₂ .2H ₂ O	b,f,g,h	Be, Pb, Hg, Ni, Al, Fe, Cr, Ce(III), Th, Zr, V(IV).	
UO ₂ (CPCA) ₂ .2H ₂ O	b	Pb, Cu, Cd, Hg, Bi, Cd, Co, Ni, Al, Fe, Ce(III), Th, V(IV), Cr(VI).	
VO(BA) ₂	i,m	Co, Ni, Zn, Fe, Al, Cr, Ti, U, Mo, W.	Steel
VO(BNA) ₂	h,j	Ag, Ti(I), Cd, Hg, Ni, Co, Mn, Zn, Al, Fe, Cr, Ti, U, Mo, W.	
VO(CPCA) ₂	i	Ag, Ti(I), Hg, Cu, Ni, Co, Zn, Fe, Al, Cr(III), Cr(VI), Ce(III), Zr, Mo, W.	
Al(BA) ₃	k,m	Cu, Cd, Zn, Ni, Co, Fe, V(V).	Bauxite
TiO(BA) ₃	d	Be, Cu, Co, Ni, Zn, Al, Fe, Ce(IV), Th, Zr, V(IV), W.	Ilmenite, Ferrotitanium
Hg(BA) ₂	e	Ag, Ti(I), Cu, Cd, Zn, Co, Ni, Fe, W.	
Hg(BNA) ₂	d,e,i	Ag, Ti(I), Cd, Cu, Bi, Co, Ni, Zn, Mn, Al, Fe, U, W.	
Hg(CPCA) ₂	e	Cu, Cd, Bi, Co, Ni, Zn, Al, Fe.	
Cu(AA) ₂	i	Pb, Cd, Zn, Mn, Ni, Fe, Al.	Brass, bronze white metal
Cd(BNA) ₂	b	Mg, Pb, Bi, Ni, Co, Mn, Zn, In, Al, Cr.	
Mn(BNA) ₂	d,e,h,j	Ag, Ti(I), Pb, Cu, Cd, Hg, Bi, Co, Ni, Zn, Al, Fe, Cr, V(IV), U, W.	
Co(BNA) ₂ .2H ₂ O	b,e,j,n	Ag, Ti(I), Pb, Cu, Cd, Hg, Bi, Ni, Zn, Mn, Fe, Al, Cr, Zr, V(IV), Mo, W.	
Ni(BNA) ₂	b,e,f,i,j	Ag, Ti(I), Pb, Cu, Cd, Hg, Bi, Co, Zn, Mn, Al, Fe, Cr, Zr, V(IV), Mo, W.	Steel, ores.
MoO ₃ (CPCA) ₂	f	Ag, Hg, Pb, Cu, Cd, Ni, Co, Bi, Fe Al, Cr, Ce(III), V(IV), Zr, W.	Molybdenite

* in the most common oxidation state

(a) Na₂-EDTA ; (b) Mg-EDTA ; (c) H₂O₂ ; (d) Tartrate ; (e) Citrate ; (f) Ascorbate ; (g) Acetate ; (h) Sulphosalicylate ; (i) F⁻ ; (j) I⁻ ; (k) CN⁻ ; (l) triethanolamine ; (m) thioglycolate ; (n) CNS⁻.

TABLE 4—SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATIONS

Reagent	Metal ion	Solvent	pH	Optimum range (p.p.m.)	Stability of colour	λ max (nm)	Molar extinction	Sensitivity $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$	Ref.
HAA	Cu(II)	CHCl_3	7.1-8.0	6-45	3 hrs	340	1×10^8	0.06	35
	U(VI)	Hexone	5.8	5.5-38	24 "	365	4.4×10^8	0.11	36
	V(IV)	TBP	5.74	1.9-6.5	16 "	338	5.6×10^8	0.01	37
	Fe(III)	Ether	3.0-7.6	1.6-10.3	4 hrs	370-375, & 490	3.8×10^8	0.20	22
HBA	Ti(IV)	CHCl_3	2.5	0.2-5.0	90 min	370(385)*	9.5×10^8	0.05	22
	Mo(VI)	Hexone	0.6-1.9	12-78	2 hrs	358(410)*	8.5×10^8	1.5	38
	U(VI)	Hexone	6.8-7.0	4.5-12.5	3 hrs	375(390)*	1.2×10^8	0.19	39
HBNA	Be(II)	CHCl_3	4.4->8.0	9-28	30 min	395(400)*	2.2×10^8	0.04	40
	U(VI)	Hexone	5.3-7.5	4-26	2 hrs	385-395 (395-415)*	1.3×10^8	0.02	41
HCPCA	Be(II)	Hexone	>7.0	0.20-0.65	>7 days	332-333	1.1×10^4	9×10^{-4}	31
	Ti(IV)	Hexone	3.0	8.5-19	75 mins	355-360	1.8×10^8	0.02	28
	U(VI)	Hexone	6.5-8.5	10.5-27	4 days	358-362	5.8×10^8	0.04	32
	Hg(II)	Hexone	>6.2	11-35	3 "	345	4.4×10^8	0.05	28

* Wave-length for measurement when different from λ_{max}

The chelates are extracted into a suitable organic solvent for the spectrophotometric determination. Isobutyl methyl ketone (hexone) is the most suitable solvent as the reagents exhibited λ_{max} at lower wave length than other common solvents. However, other solvents like chloroform ether and tributylphosphate (TBP) have also been used. HCPCA is the best reagent for spectrophotometry.

HCPCA is almost specific for beryllium in the presence of $\text{Na}_2\text{-EDTA}$ and for uranium(VI) in the presence of Mg-EDTA. Citrate is used as the masking agent for diverse ions in the estimation of mercury(II) with HCPCA. Table 5 gives the list of metal ions separated and the masking agents used in the extraction of spectrophotometric determination of metal ions with β -ketoanilides.

Applications in Titrimetric Analysis

An indirect method for the titrimetric determination of beryllium has been developed by the quantitative bromination of HAA⁴² or HCPCA³¹. Freshly precipitated $\text{Be}(\text{AA})_2$ or $\text{Be}(\text{CPCA})_2$ is dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and an excess of a standard solution of bromatebromide mixture is added when one bromine gets attached to the *para*-position in the phenyl group and another in the active methylene group. Beryllium can be determined from the amount of excess bromine by iodometric titration. However, the bromine atom attached to the active methylene group is slowly liberated unless the titration is rapid. Thus 1.4-3.5 mg of beryllium has been determined with relative standard deviation of $\pm 0.4\%$.

TABLE 5—SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION IN THE PRESENCE OF FOREIGN IONS

Complex	Masking agent	Foreign ions*	Application
Be(II)-HBNA	b	Pb, Cu, Co, Ni, Zn, Al, Fe, Cr.	Beryl
Be(II)-CPCA	a	Ag, Ti(I), Cd, Hg, Cu, Pb, Co, Ni, Bi, Al, Ga, In, Cr, Fe, Ce(III), Th, Zr, V(IV), U, W.	
U(VI)-HAA	b	Cu, Cd, Mn, Al, Fe, Cr, Ce(IV), Th, V(V), Mo, W.	Uraninite
U(VI)-HBA	b	Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba, Hg, Cd, Zn, Pb, Mn, Co, Ni, Bi, Fe, Al, Ce(III), V(IV), Th, Cr(VI), Mo.	
U(VI)-HBNA	b, h	Ag, Ti(I), Be, Pb, Cu, Cd, Hg, Bi, Ba, Sr, Ni, Co, Fe, Al, Cr(III), Cr(VI), Ga, In, Ce(III), Th, Zr, V(IV), Mo.	Uraninite
U(VI)-HCPCA	b	Ag, Ti(I), Pb, Hg, Cd, Cu, Co, Bi, Ni, Zn, Al, Fe, Ce, Th, Zr, V(IV), Cr(VI), Mo.	
Ti(IV)-HBA	-	Be, Ni, Co, Mn, Fe, Al, Ce(IV), Th, V(IV), U, Mo.	Bauxite, Ilmenite, Ferrotitanium.
Ti(IV)-HCPCA	-	Ag, Ti(I), Hg, Pb, Ni, Co, Al, Fe, Th, V(IV), Mo.	
V(IV)-HAA	k	Ni, Co, Zn, Mn, Fe, Al, Cr, U, Mo, W.	Steel
Mo(VI)-HBA	f	Be, Ni, Co, Zn, Mn, Al, Cr, Fe, Ce, Th, U.	
Cu(II)-HAA	-	Mg, Ca, Ba, Pb, Hg, Zn, Bi, Co, Ni, Mn, Al.	Brass, bronze White metal Bauxite
Fe(III)-HBA	-	Tl, Be, Cd, Hg, Co, Ni, Zn, Mn, Bi, Al, Cr, Ti, U, Mo.	
Hg(II)-HCPCA	e	Cu, Cd, Co, Ni, Zn, Al.	

* In the most common oxidation state

a, b etc—see table 3

Studies on the complexes of β -ketoanilides and substituted β -ketoanilides

A great deal of work has been done on the complexes of HAA and the effect of substitution in HAA on its complexes. According to Harries *et al*^{4,5,44} the formation of $\text{Be}(\text{AA})_2$ has been found to have a less favourable enthalpy but more favourable entropy change than the acetylacetone chelation though the corresponding data for protonation were comparable. The phenyl group of HAA is probably coplanar with the chelate ring of the H-bonded enol form of the reagent.

Kettrup *et al*^{7,8} have studied the effect of substitution of nitro, chloro, methyl and methoxy groups in different positions of the anilide ring and have explained the stability of beryllium and uranium chelates in the light of electronic and mesomeric effect. The *o*-substituted compounds are less stable probably due to steric effect but otherwise the relation between the stability and pK_a is linear. But Harries *et al*^{4,5} have observed that the stability of Be^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} chelates of *o*-substituted HAA is a function of the basic strength of the donor atom and steric effect of the ring substitution is not significant. Similar correlation between the stabilities of copper chelates of chloro- and bromo-substituted HAA has also been reported^{45,46}. The extraction behaviour of copper chelates of several reagents of general formula, CH_3 .CO.CH₂.CO.NHR have also been studied⁴⁷. Replacement of the aromatic group by some less polar alkyl groups in the position of R reduces the extractive power.

Analytical Uses of Thio-derivatives of β -ketoanilides

Mono- and dithio-derivatives of β -ketoanilides are expected to be better reagents for the class-b type or border region^{18, 19} metal ions. Copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes of thiodibenzoylmethane, C_6H_5 .CO.CH₂.CS.C₆H₅ extract at lower pH and with smaller amounts of reagent than the corresponding dioxocompound.

Dithio-acetoacetanilide is difficult to prepare due to dimerisation but the mono-thio compound, acetothioacetanilide, (HATA), CH_3 .CO.CH₂.CS.NH.C₆H₅ of pK_a 11.6 (in 50% acetone) is easy to prepare⁴⁸. This is a fine reagent for the extraction of photometric determination of iron(III)⁵⁰, cobalt(II)⁵⁰, nickel(II)⁵⁰, ruthenium(III)⁵¹, osmium(VIII)⁵¹ and selenium(IV)⁵². HATA reacts better with the 'border region' metal ions of the eighth group of the periodic table than the 'class-b' metal ions of the same group. The determination of osmium is possible in the presence of Ru, Pt, Pd, Rh, Ir, Au, Ag, Ni, Co, Zn, Mn, Cd, Bi, Pb, As, Sn and Fe. Ruthenium has also been determined in the presence of most of these metal ions. but the tolerance limit is lower than the same for osmium. Tellurium does not interfere in the estimation of selenium.

Gravimetric analysis using HATA requires sufficient excess of the reagent than the theoretical amount as the reagent is highly soluble in water. However, HATA

has been found to be an excellent gravimetric reagent for mercury(II)⁵³. The precipitation is quantitative at pH 1.3-1.8 and Be, Mg, Pb, Mn, Zn, Cd, Cu, Ni, Co, Sb, Bi, Cr(III), Ti, Zr, Ce, V(IV), V(V), Mo(VI) and Te(VI) do not interfere in the presence of Na_2 -EDTA. Cobalt(II)⁵⁴, Nickel(II)⁵⁴, Zinc(II)⁵³ and Cadmium(II)⁵³, have also been determined gravimetrically and separated from allied metal ions using HATA.

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References

1. J. DAS and S. BANERJEE, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1961, **184**, 110.
2. H. J. HARRIES, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 519.
3. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.
4. R. C. PAUL, 'New Pathways in Inorganic Chemistry', Gen. Eds. E. A. V. EBSWORTH, A. G. MADDOCK and A. G. SHARPE, Cambridge Univ. Press, 1968, p. 240.
5. A. KETTERUP and W. RIEPE, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1970, **252**, 1.
6. L. G. VAN UITERT, W. C. FERNELIUS and B. E. DOUGLAS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 457.
7. A. KETTERUP and H. SPECKER, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **246**, 108.
8. A. KETTERUP, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **246**, 183.
9. H. DIEHL, 'The Application of the Dioximes to Analytical Chemistry', G. F. Smith Co., Columbus, Ohio, 1940.
10. G. SCHWARZENBACH and A. ACKERMAN, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1949, **32**, 1682.
11. 'Merck Index', 6th Ed., 1952, p. 844.
12. E. C. HORNING, (Editor), 'Organic Synthesis' Vol. III, 1960, p. 10, J. WILEY, N. Y.
13. C. F. H. ALLEN and W. J. HUMPHLETT, 'Organic Synthesis', Ed. N. ROBJOHN, Coll. Vol. IV, J. Wiley, N. Y., 1963, p. 30.
14. J. M. STRALEY and A. C. ADAMS, 'Organic Synthesis', Ed. N. ROBJOHN, Coll. Vol. IV, J. Wiley, N. Y., 1963, p. 415.
15. A. K. SARKAR and J. DAS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1967, **39**, 1608.
16. A. WEISBERGER, C. J. KIBLER and R. V. YOUNG, Eastman Kodak Co. U. S. PATENT, 2, 412, 700; Dec. 17, 1946, *Chem. Abs.*, 1947, **41**, 1702.
17. H. C. BARANEY and M. PIANCA, *J. Chem. Soc. (London)*, 1947, 1420.
18. S. AHRLAND, J. CHATT and N. R. DAVIS, *Quarterly Reviews*, 1958, **12**, 265.
19. R. G. PEARSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 3533.
20. A. K. SARKAR and J. DAS, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 507.
21. A. K. SARKAR and J. DAS, *Analyt. Letters*, 1968, **1**, 323.
22. A. K. SARKAR and J. DAS, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1971, **254**, 364.
23. S. K. MANDAL and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 424.

24. N. K. CHAUDHURI and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 525.
25. N. K. CHAUDHURI and J. DAS, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 1398.
26. N. K. CHAUDHURI and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 446.
27. S. K. MANDAL and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1146.
28. S. K. MANDAL and J. DAS, Unpublished work.
29. S. K. MANDAL and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 631.
30. P. K. DAN and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (accepted for publication).
31. N. K. CHAUDHURI and J. DAS, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **57**, 193.
32. S. K. MANDAL, N. K. CHAUDHURI and J. DAS, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1975, **80**, 399.
33. N. K. CHAUDHURI and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 33.
34. S. K. MANDAL and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 134.
35. A. K. SARKAR and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 817.
36. A. K. SARKAR, *Indian J. Technology*, 1973, **11**, 272.
37. K. DUTTA and J. DAS, *Indian J. Technology*, 1972, **10**, 76.
38. A. K. SARKAR and J. DAS, *Analyt. Letters*, 1969, **2**, 141.
39. N. K. CHAUDHURI and J. DAS, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1971, **255**, 34.
40. N. K. CHAUDHURI and J. DAS, Unpublished work.
41. S. K. MANDAL, N. K. CHAUDHURI and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 685.
42. J. DAS and S. BANERJEE, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1962, **188**, 109.
43. H. J. HARRIES, S. SAVAGE, G. WRIGHT and L. LOGAN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 2477.
44. H. J. HARRIES and G. WRIGHT, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 3149.
45. A. KETTRUP and J. ABSHAGEN, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1970, **25b**, 1382.
46. A. KETTRUP and J. ABSHAGEN, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1970, **25b**, 1386.
47. H. J. HARRIES and K. WELLER, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 547.
48. E. UHLEMAN and H. MUELLER, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1968, **41**, 311.
49. G. BARNIKOW, H. KUNZEK and D. RICHTER, *Ann. Chem.*, 1966, **49**, 495.
50. K. DUTTA and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1026.
51. K. DUTTA and J. DAS, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14**, 917.
52. T. PAL and J. DAS, Convention of Indian Chemists Bangalore, Dec., 1976.
53. T. PAL and J. DAS, unpublished work.
54. K. DUTTA and J. DAS, unpublished work.